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Annotation: *Translation performed an important social function, making cross-language communication possible. The spread of written translations has given people access to the cultural achievements of other peoples and made it possible to exchange literatures and cultures.*

Key words: *Translation, language, principles, linguistic, science, teaching, methods, theory, communication.*

The founders of the theory of translation were the translators themselves, who wanted to combine their own experience and the experience of their fellow professionals. It is clear that the statement of their "translation credo" was stated by the most famous translators of their time, and although the thoughts they expressed did not meet modern scientific requirements and did not fit into consistent theoretical concepts, a certain number of such conjectures are still interesting today.

For example, the question of the degree of proximity of the translation to the original was already discussed by translators of the ancient world. In the first translations of the Bible, which was considered exemplary and sacred, the desire to completely copy the original was outweighed, which led to ambiguity and complete incomprehensibility of the translation. Later, some translators tried to provide a theoretical justification for the translator's right to greater freedom in relation to the original, the need to reproduce the meaning or the general "charm"

of the original. In the first statements, on the goals that the translator should be guided by, you can find the beginning of the theoretical disputes of our day on the possibility of making a literal or free translation, on the need to preserve in translation the same effect on the reader that the original has; and so on.

Some translators expressed some semblance of "norms of translation theory", suggesting requirements that a "good" translator had to comply with. The poet and translator Etienne Dolet proposed the following basic principles of translation:

- a. understand the content of the translated text and the thoughts of the author being translated;
- b. be proficient in the language from which it translates, and equally proficient in the language into which it translates;
- c. try to avoid the tendency to translate verbatim, because this distorts the content of the original and destroys the beauty of its form;
- d. common forms of speech should not be used in translation;
- e. correctly select and arrange words, reproducing the overall impression that the original text makes in the appropriate "tone".

In the book of the Englishman A. Tytler "Translation and principles", the main requirements for translation were stated as follows:

- a. the translation must fully reflect the ideas of the original;
- b. the manner of presentation of the translation should be the same as in the original;
- c. like the original, the translation should be easy to read.

These requirements are still significant, although they are obvious to us today.

Translators' statements about the principles they follow in their work are of great interest and are carefully studied by translation researchers, but they do not constitute at least some translation theory, and even more so they are not able to replace it. The principles and recommendations derived and expressed from translation practice are indisputable in themselves, but since they were not based on any theory that would reveal the essence of translation, they usually affect only

the superficial aspects of translation activity.

The first attempts to explain the importance of scientific analysis of translators' activities caused a wave of criticism on their part. Translators saw in them the desire to introduce freedom of creativity, to create some rules and norms of translation, which the translator will have to follow. The theory of translation was perceived by them as something fundamentally negative and even threatening to the art of translation. Strictly speaking, the science of translation is impossible, since translation is a skill unattainable by scientific analysis and division.

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